

EVALUATION OF BIODEGRADABLE WASTE AS MANURE FOR TERRACE GARDEN**M.I. Niyas Ahamed**

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*Corresponding Author: driniyasahamed@shctpt.edu**ABSTRACT**

Communities will grow more congested as civilizations become more wealthy and urbanized. As a result, trash disposal, particularly biodegradable waste, will become more difficult since it will be thrown in the streets, having a detrimental effect on both human health and the environment. This biodegradable waste can be turned into vegetable manure for the terrace garden, which would lessen the immediate family needs. Terrace gardening not only helps households obtain fresh produce free of chemicals but also returns some land to agriculture.

Keywords: Negative impact, Manure, Chemical-free, Biodegradable waste

1. INTRODUCTION

The need for the production of organic food in agriculture, which is quickly becoming an appealing source of income generating, is the result of an increased awareness of health and environmental challenges in agriculture. These days, cultivating vegetables has evolved into an economic activity that may be classified as a company. Products labeled as organic have been produced in accordance with a method of agriculture that forgoes the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides in favor of tending to one's social and environmental responsibilities. This type of farming is effective at the grass roots level, preserving the reproductive and regenerative capacity of the soil. It also produces nutritious food rich in vitality that is resistant to diseases. Good plant nutrition and sound soil management are also important components of this type of farming (Thiripurasundari 2015). When purchasing veggies at the grocery store, you run the risk of ingesting traces of pesticides and other agricultural pollutants. The cultivators employ an excessive amount of chemical fertilizers and pesticides in order to increase their yield and hence their income. The majority of farmers aren't able to determine the precise amount of fertiliser or pesticide to use, so they just throw it on, assuming that the more fertiliser they use, the better the crop will turn out. As a direct consequence of this, the vast majority of the vegetables that are offered for sale in the market contain hazardous compounds. however, the vegetables that you cultivate yourself on your terrace at home won't be exposed to any of those chemicals. It is simple to convert all biodegradable garbage into organic manure that can

then be used for the cultivation of vegetables. In most cases, these wastes are tossed about the house or on the road, which pollutes the environment to a very severe degree and encourages the hatching of mosquitoes and flies. On the other hand, one can easily picture how much cleaner and healthier the environment would be if all of these wastes were transformed into manure for terrace vegetable gardens.

2. THE AIMS OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT

This study was undertaken with the following goals in mind in light of the realization that the recycling of biodegradable trash and its application for terrace garden is more pertinent to the current situation than was previously thought.

- 1) To interview residents in their homes to identify potential participants in the study.
- 2) To conduct a scientific investigation (as the investigator) in order to evaluate the quality of the standardised pot mix.
- 3) To investigate how well these pot mixes work for the growth of vegetables and greens.
- 4) To organise the training for the respondents who were chosen from both urban and rural settings.

3. THE COMPONENTS AND PROCEDURES

The approach that was taken for this study included conducting a survey of households, participating in a training programme, conducting an experimental study of pot mix, and analysing the growth of greens and vegetables grown in terrace gardens.

3.1. Survey of households and educational opportunities

For the household survey, a total of 700 Salem district residents were chosen as respondents, with 500 coming from urban areas and 200 coming from rural areas. A pre-structured interview schedule was utilised in the administration of the survey. The results of the household survey were used to develop a training module that would last for five days and emphasise the importance of recycling biodegradable waste for the preparation of manure and its use in organic terrace gardens. This module was developed based on the information that was collected.

3.2 Experimental Study

The investigator conducted an experimental research on various techniques for making manure from biodegradable garbage. This manure offers an organic composition that enhances a crop's biological, chemical, and physical characteristics. Household kitchen trash plays a significant part in organic systems, along with biodegradable waste, animal manure, and crop residues. In addition to completing the nutrient cycle and providing nitrogen for plant growth, compost generated from biodegradable waste also improves the biological, physical, and chemical characteristics of the soil and serves as a valuable supply of nutrients and energy for the soil eco system. Additionally, they increase the amount of nutrients in the soil and aid to alter its physical characteristics by enhancing the soil's ability to hold water, aerate it, make the drainage friable, and give organic matter a darker hue (Viswanath 2014).

The researcher conducts an experiment while keeping in mind the advantages listed above.

- Experiment 1

The process for making potting mix involves gathering eggshells, vegetable and fruit peels,

tea and coffee grounds, and other biodegradable garbage. Put these wastes in a 3-by-4-foot plastic pail each day. As soon as the bucket is full, 250 grammes of cow dung are diluted with 1/2 litre of water and added to the waste. The bucket is covered with a small cotton cloth and kept in shade. Shake the bucket to mix the contents thoroughly after 35 days have passed. Use the prepared manure right away for the terrace garden to create a very messy, dark manure.

- Experiment 2

In the second approach, trash from homes was gathered, dried, and combined with additional materials such coco peat, ash, and need cake. The drying capacity for these methods ranges from 2 to 5 days, depending on the heat intensity. The second way involves quickly preparing the manure so that it can be used as needed Below is a list of the components used in two different potting mixes:

Pot Mix 1		Pot Mix – 2	
Coirpith	30%	Coirpith	25%
Compostedkitchen waste	30%	Compostedkitchen waste	25%
Farm yard manure	30%	Farm yard manure	25%
Ash	10%	Red soil	25%

In order to compare the two potting mixes, the researcher used them to produce vegetables and greens on a terrace. With the exception of red soil and ash, the first three components of potting mix were typical. Twenty grammes of neem cake and the four ingredients were added in the specified amounts, mixed thoroughly, and then put into a grow bag that was one foot by one foot in size. Selected greens and vegetables were planted with seeds and seedlings, and the progress of the plants was constantly monitored every 10 days. 3.3 Vegetable and leafy greens growth evaluation. The experiment was conducted using two types of standardised potting soil and the identical kinds of vegetables and greens. For the original trial, the natural vegetables and greens of the Salem district were chosen, including the following: Vegetables: Tomato, Chilli, Brinjal, Ladies finger, Bitter guard.

S.No	Duration	Growth rate of greens (cm)									
		Palak		Sirukeerai		Thandukeerai		Fenugreek		Mint	
		*P-1	*P-2	P-1	P-2	P-1	P-2	P-1	P-2	P-1	P-2
1	0-10	2	2	1	4	3	5	3	4	3	3
2	11-20	5	7	11	20	15	20	10	16	5	12
3	21-30	11	14	16	25	19	24	12	20	12	17
4	31-40	15	19	19	31	26	29	18	24	15	19
5	41-50	18	-	22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table-1

Greens include fenugreek, palak, thandukeerai, mint, and sirukeerai. Once every ten days, the measuring tape was used to track the growth of the vegetables and greens. Table 1 and the following information provide the growth rates of the greens grown in terrace gardens

The development of five different varieties of greens on two categories of pot mixes with somewhat different ingredients is shown in the table and figure above. When compared to the pot mix 1 with ash, the pot mix 2 with red soil exhibits a better growth rate for greens.

Vegetable growth rates in potting mixes 1 and 2 are shown in Table 2.

Figure – 1 & 2

S.No	Duration	Growth rate of Vegetables (cm)									
		Tomato		Brinjal		Chilli		Ladies finger		Bitter gourd	
		*P-1	*P-2	P-1	P-2	P-1	P-2	P-1	P-2	P-1	P-2
1	0-10	2	10	10	13	13	10	10	3	3	2
2	11-20	11	13	15	19	14	18	9	13	9	7
3	21-30	14	17	22	28	17	33	15	20	15	19
4	31-40	19	26	28	42	26	39	21	28	25	36
5	41-50	29	42	33	48	32	42	25	33	33	42
6	51-60	36	48	38	55	41	54	36	45	49	59

Table 2

Figure-3&4

The aforementioned table and figure make it clear that vegetables develop more quickly in potting mix 2 than they do in potting mix 1. Therefore, it is recommended to include red soil while

preparing potting mix along with other elements. Comparing the height of the bitter guard to that of the brinjal (55 cm) and the chilli (54 cm) in the pot mix throughout the course of the 60 days, bitter guard had reached a height of 56 cm.

4. CONCLUSION

Fertile agricultural land has been converted into homes and other infrastructures as a result of people moving to metropolitan areas, leaving less space for farming. Nearly 60% of people will reside in cities by 2030. The terrace garden can use organic waste from homes as manure, which lowers pollution. So, using earthworms to compost all household trash from the kitchen is an option. It is possible to gather biodegradable waste, particularly kitchen waste, from a chosen neighborhood of Salem district homes and recycle it similarly to organic manure.

References

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